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XolovaMuyassar Abdulhakimovana

Termiz davlat universiteti,

(PhD) o'zbek tilshunosligi kafedrasida katta o'ituvchisi

ORCID: 0000-0002-7604-2958, xolovam@tersu.uz

O'ZBEK SHEVASI ONLAYN LUG'ATINING MA'LUMOTLAR BAZASI VA QIPCHOQ LAHJASINING INGLIZ TILIGA TARJIMASI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10157552>**ANNOTATSIYA**

[1] kirish: korpus tilshunosligidagi dialektlarning roli haqidagi umumiy nazariyalarga asoslangan ushbu maqola dialektning mashina tarjimasidagi birinchi bosqichi bo'lgan o'zbek dialektlaridan biri bo'lgan qipchoq lahjasining onlayn lug'at ma'lumotlar bazasi interfeysi va uning ingliz tiliga tarjima haqidagi qarashlar Surxondaryo viloyatining Baysun dialektining misolida onlayn lug'atda o'z ifodasini topdi; [2] metod: hududlar bo'yicha ekspeditsiyalarda olib borilgan tadqiqotlar davomida kuzatish usuli, dialektlarning transkripsiyaviy hosilasida grafik tavsif, dialektning semantikasini dekodlash referat, dialekt tarjimalari mazmuni bo'yicha o'zbek-ingliz leksemalarining muqobil usuli dan foydalanilgan; [3] yechim va natija: jami 502 leksemaning ingliz tiliga tarjimalari. onlayn dialekt lug'atlari ma'lumotlar bazasiga kiritilgan va izohlangan; [4] xulosa: to'g'ridan-to'g'ri ingliz tiliga tarjima qilingan o'zbek tilining qipchoq lahjasining fonetik variantlari, standart tildan leksik farqlarga ega bo'lgan dialektning variantlari, tarjima izohlar bilan brilgan, etnik aholining turmush tarzida farq qiladigan leksemalar ingliz tiliga tarjimasiz kiritilishi kerak degan xulosalar berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: o'zbek lahjasi; dialekt lug'ati; dialekt bazalari; dialekt tarjimasida; onlayn lug'at imkoniyatlari; dialekt onlayn ma'lumotlar bazalari.

Муяссар Холова

(PhD) Кафедра узбекского языкознания,

Термезского государственного университета,

ORCID: 0000-0002-7604-2958

190100 Термез, Узбекистан, xolovam@tersu.uz

БАЗА ДАННЫХ ОНЛАЙН-СЛОВАРЯ УЗБЕКСКОГО ДИАЛЕКТА И ПРИМЕЧАНИЯ ПО ПЕРЕВОДУ КИПЧАКСКОГО ДИАЛЕКТА НА АНГЛИЙСКИЙ**АННОТАЦИЯ**

[1] предыстория: В этой статье, основанной на общих теориях о роли диалектов в корпусной лингвистике, ее первом этапе в машинном переводе, дается описание интерфейса онлайн-словарной базы данных кипчакского диалекта, одного из узбекских диалектов, а также взглядов на перевод этот диалект в онлайн-словаре нашел свое выражение на примере байсунского диалекта Сурхандарьинской области; [2] методы: метод наблюдения во время исследований в экспедициях по регионам, графическое описание в транскрипционном

производном диалектов, реферат при расшифровке семантики диалекта, альтернативный метод узбекско-английских лексем по содержанию диалектных переводов; [3] результаты: переводы на английский язык в общей сложности 502 лексем. включены и аннотированы в базу данных диалектных онлайн-словарей; [4] выводы: фонетические варианты кипчакского диалекта узбекского языка, переведенные непосредственно на английский, варианты диалекта, имеющие лексические отличия от стандартного языка, предпочтительно переводить с аннотациями, те лексемы, которые имеют различия в образе жизни этнического населения, следует вводить в английский язык без перевода.

Ключевые слова: узбекский диалект; диалектный словарь; диалектные базы; диалектный перевод; возможности онлайн-словаря; диалектные онлайн-базы данных.

Muyassar Kholova

ORCID: 0000-0002-7604-2958

(PhD) Department of Languages, Termez State University,
190100 Termez, Uzbekistan. xolovam@tersu.uz

DATABASE OF THE UZBEK DIALECT ONLINE DICTIONARY AND NOTES ON THE TRANSLATION OF THE KIPCHAK DIALECT INTO ENGLISH

ABSTRACT

[1] background: In this article, based on general theories about the role of dialects in corpus linguistics, its first stage in machine translation, the description of the interface of the online dictionary database of the Kipchak dialect, one of the Uzbek dialects, as well as views on the translation of this dialect in the online dictionary, have found their expression on the example of the Baysun dialect of Surkhandarya region; methods: [2] method of observation during research in expeditions across regions, graphic description in the transcriptional derivative of dialects, abstract in deciphering the semantics of the dialect, alternative method of Uzbek-English tokens on the content of dialect translations; [3] results: English translations of a total of 502 tokens are included and annotated in the database of dialect online dictionaries; [4] conclusions: phonetic variants of the Kipchak dialect of the Uzbek language, translated directly to English, dialect variants that have lexical differences from the standard language should preferably be translated with annotations, those tokens that have differences in the lifestyle of the ethnic population should be introduced into English without translation.

Keywords: uzbek dialect; dialect dictionary; dialect bases; dialect translation; online dictionary features; dialect online databases.

Introduction. Imagining all aspects of public life without digital media is tricky in world linguistics. In time, linguists don't want to spend more time collecting examples from books that support their research theories. Therefore, it is necessary to develop dictionaries that satisfy such scientific needs. Also, the need for innovation in the lexicography of linguistics has led to the emergence of electronic dictionaries in the online form, and for such electronic language databases to "live" in their activities, their dictionaries in the form of books must have more features. We know that expeditions to rural areas are organized to study and research dialects. Mahmud Kashgari, during his travels, classified the Turkic languages and their dialects based not on linguistic or geographical features but on ethnic features [1].

The impact of the development of rural infrastructure on the language, the change in the dialect in the language of the ethnic population due to the mass media and communication, telephone, Internet, etc., the gradual penetration of the standard language into the elements of the dialect presents us with the urgent task of creating a single dialectological database that includes dialect information that has been preserved dialects in the language of the older generation and is still kept in private libraries. As a result, it becomes possible to study dialects of a language not only linguistically but also from a practical point of view, thereby preserving and passing on dialect units from generation to generation.

Referring to the research experience of combining language elements and the study of language corpora, English Dialect Attachment (EDA) and English Dialect Attachment Corpus (EDAC) were introduced in 2018. For this, an application was developed for Android devices, and 47,000 people living in the UK marked the dialect variants in their area from 26 selected words. Also, more than 3,500 respondents provided audio recordings of these dialects, and a conclusion was made about the dialect's scope [2]. The impact of the development of rural infrastructure on the language, the change in the dialect in the language of the ethnic population due to the mass media and communication, telephone, Internet, etc., the gradual penetration of the standard language into the elements of the dialect presents us with the urgent task of creating a single dialectological database that includes dialect information that has been preserved dialects in the language of the older generation and is still kept in private libraries. As a result, it becomes possible to study dialects of a language not only linguistically but also from a practical point of view, thereby preserving and passing on dialect units from generation to generation. Referring to the research experience of combining language elements and the study of language corpora, English Dialect Attachment (EDA) and English Dialect Attachment Corpus (EDAC) were introduced in 2018. For this, an application was developed for Android devices, and 47,000 people living in the UK marked the dialect variants in their area from 26 selected words. Also, more than 3,500 respondents provided audio recordings of these dialects, and a conclusion was made about the dialect's scope[2].

Farhan V. submitted his work on unsupervised translation of Arabic dialects within the database of Arabic dialects. In it, the dialect is not reflected in the parallel educational corpus, and there are two systems of this practice: the first is the model of translation from the dialect into the literary language (literary language), and the second system is based on the Google NMT (GNMT) system. The author mentions that systems must first be evaluated in a controlled environment; tokens will be compared using parallel Jordanian and Modern Standard Arabic (MSA) corpora and then transferred to an automatic translation environment [3]. Kaddura S., assessing the place of dialects in the social network, emphasizes that the sphere of influence of the dialect is more comprehensive than that of the standard language. Based on the experience of creating a dialectological corpus of Bashkir linguistics, in order to prevent the heterogeneity of dialect foundations, he believes that practice should be carried out in three areas: a lexicological base, a collection of dialect cards, and a base of dialect texts. The scientific project by Sirazitdinov Z. is focused on analyzing phonetic, semantic, and morphological dialectisms of dialect units, including the analysis of 52 thousand dialect language units [4] as a practical work on the placement of the language in the corpus, linguistic models of different language levels have been developed [5] and in the educational corpus of the Uzbek language [6] - a morphologically annotated corpus of all units that make up the Uzbek linguistics. as part of teaching the Uzbek language.

In Uzbek linguistics in the Uzbek electronic corpus [7] as a practical work on the placement of the language in the corpus, linguistic models of different language levels have been developed [8] and in the educational corpus of the Uzbek language [9] - a morphologically annotated corpus of all units that make up the Uzbek linguistics. as part of teaching the Uzbek language [10]. The language has its conditions for bringing it to the world level. One is that the language must have the following foundations for its linguistically annotated bases at different levels:

- a) The phonetic base of the language;
- b) The semantic base of the language;
- c) Morphological basis of the language;
- d) The dialectological basis of the language;
- e) The syntactic structural basis of the language.

Although the research is being carried out as part of the construction of the corpus of the Uzbek language, our research on the construction of its dialect base and corpus [11] is the beginning of work, and these studies are relevant today [12].

Dialect database interface. The interface is a technical and software combination prepared in the database, which ensures the interaction and transition of control, measuring, and various task devices. It also allows researchers to synchronize information, encode a system of modules, and make

mechanical and electrical connections of devices for collecting signals, i.e., data. [13]. Designing a dialect vocabulary base requires adapting its appearance to the internal essence while attention is paid to its design. Every case study that focuses on requires a high level of design. An essential factor in the corpus is using photographs that reflect national identity ("otav" - mobile home for livestock breeders, national clothes, jewelry, drawings depicting traditions and customs). For example, most residents of the Baysun district of the Surkhandarya region are representatives of the Kypchak dialect, and their lifestyle is mainly focused on growing livestock products. Based on the population's lifestyle, the spirit of fidelity to past ancestors, and the current national views, the external interface of the base was presented with the image of an original resident of the population engaged in animal husbandry [14]

1 figure.

Presentation of dialect bases

Materials and Methods. Since our research was one of the first studies in creating a dialect database of the Uzbek language, an expedition was organized with students to the Baysun district, one of the districts of the Surkhandarya region. The observation method was used to study interviews with residents and their way of life. Enrichment of the dialect vocabulary base with dialect lexemes, both in oral and written form, brings perfection. Therefore, the description method was used to explain the dialects mentioned in the epics, recorded and published by the "bakhshi" (those who sing national songs with the help of the "dumbira" – national musical instrument) living in the Baysun region. Baysun district was founded in 1926. The area of the district is 3.25 square meters km. The number of microdistricts is 39, settlements 54, and rural settlements 49 [15]. In Uzbek linguistics, there are phonetic differences in the pronunciation of the standard language and dialect, as well as in the interaction of the population using three dialects: Kypchak, Karluk, and Oguz. To fix this problem and create convenience for the researcher when using the online dictionary, the standard language, transliteration, and transcription of the dialect were reflected in the database using a graphical description method:

1 table.

Standard language	transliteration	Transcription	English language
Ona	Yena	<i>Jenä</i>	Mom
Uyqu	Uyqi	<i>Üjqı</i>	Sleep
To' rva	To' rba	<i>Törba</i>	Bag

Three different graphic variants of the Uzbek dialect

With the help of the interpretation method, the meaning of lexemes in the Uzbek-English language, which reflects the way of life, mentality, and linguistic and cultural life of the ethnic population, is annotated. The statistics method is used for morphological, lexico-semantic, etymological sorting, and statistics of words in the dictionary base.

Results. This database is intended for a wide range of users, and upon request, the following parts of the database are provided to the user:

1. Homepage.
2. Table of words.
3. About the project.
4. Transcription.
5. Communication.

The home page expression in the dialect database. To give a general idea of the dialect base, the interface of this page consists of 0.60 percent windows with a picture reflecting the national mentality, culture and spirituality consists of 0.40 percent and this 0.40 percent window is divided into 3 external ones: morphological, etymological statistics.

1 cell. The conclusion of a general morphological analyzer based on the dialect's external statistics is presented. (based on an independent category - 492; a group of auxiliary categories - 3; a separate category - 7)

2 cell. The most recent examples of language units added to the database are presented in transliterated form, which increases the level of user experience, taking into account the use by a broad audience: “jaloq” (a plate from which a dog eats), “jaltibosh” (a bald or completely shaved person), “jamov” (cloth attached to a torn or pierced part of a garment), “jalpaymaq” (prone lying), “jalpoq” (flat, glued to the ground), Etc. are listed.

3 cell. The etymology of dialect words is given: Persian (62), Arabic (16), Mongolian (2), as well as the statistics of arrival from English and French, which passed through the Russian language.

2 table.

In the word table section of the dialect dictionary

Options for using the language database		
	Facilities	Demonstration
	standard language	Ayirmoq
	Transliteration	Ayirib taylamaq
	Transcription	<i>ājirib tajlamāq</i>
	The category	Fe'l/verb
	interpretation	Uloqni ko'pkari, ot o'yinida, so'yilgan echki bolasini bir necha da'vogarlarining ichidan yulib olish va belgilangan joyda hammadan oldin ko'rsatilgan joyga eltib tashlamoq [In the national equestrian game, to snatch a slain goat from several rivals and deliver it to the specified place before everyone else]
	Example	Guloyim shartillatib uloqti yulib ketib, ayirib tashladi.
	Synonym	Bo'laklamoq (Ad.t.) ajratmoq (Ad.t.)
	Homonyms	-
	Antonym	Qo'shmoq Žapištiruv (sheva)
	Etymology	Uzbek
	Russian translation	РАЗДЕЛИТЬ
	English translation	Divide

Representation of tokens in the dialect database

Problems of translating dialects in the database of online dictionaries.

For the past 35 years, learners of English as a foreign language have used Google as their primary translation tool (Assim S. Alrajhi, 2023). Abraham Lee experimented with participants in a Spanish course to provide feedback and translation solutions through websites (Lee Abraham, 2009). This translation method is mainly used by users who prepare written information. From a linguistic point of view, we know that dialects have more meaning, description, and semantic scope than standard languages, and we should not ignore these parameters in translating a dialect dictionary into English. It is possible to use translations of lexemes, words, sentences, and grammatical units related to the Uzbek standard language, but this system still needs to reflect translations of Uzbek dialects. That shows a need for translation dictionaries of Uzbek dialects into English. In our online dictionary database, the translation of dialects into English is reflected on the basis of the following approaches:

1. Translation of dialects with phonetic differences into English.
2. Translation of dialects with lexical differences into English.
3. Semantic translation of dialects:
 - comment on the material;
 - translation into material and related reality.

As an example of the dialects of the Uzbek language, we consider the dictionary of the Baysun dialects of the Surkhandarya region and believe that the difference between dialects is mainly based on phonetic differences and related to their translation. Solving the problem by connecting them to the Standard Language Translation is possible. However, the way of life, lexical units representing the national culture, ethnographic views, and linguocultural atmosphere need a complex and explanatory translation. Below is information on three different translation methods in the categories section of 502 lexemes in the general online dictionary.

3 table

The total number of lexemes is 502. (categories)	English translation of dialects with phonetic variations.(326)	Combined translation of dialects with lexical distinguishing features into English.(77)	Semantic translation of dialects with lexical difference: a/b (99)
Ot/noun (332)	188	70	74
Sifat/adjective (47)	38	2	7
Son/number (1)	1	-	-
Olmosh/pronoun (2)	1		1
Fe'l/verb (102)	86	3	13
Ravish/adverb (8)	7	1	
Bog'lovchi/ Conjunction (3)	3	-	-
Modal so'zlar/ Modal words (1)			1
Undov so'zlar/ Exclamative sentence (4)	2		2
Taqlid so'zlar/ Interjection (2)		1	1

statistics of translation into English of tokens by category

2 figure

3 figure

4 figure

Discussion.

English translation of dialects with phonetic variations.

This translation method paid primary attention to dialects with phonetic differences from the standard language. For example, most of these units, observed with their phonetic variations in the Uzbek standard language, are tokens with English translations. The section in this category has a statistically significant number of phonetically distinct dialects. Noun group – 332, adjective word group – 38 number word group – 1, pronoun word group - 1, verb word group - 86, adverb word group - 7, Conjunction word group – 3, and was not Modal words, Exclamative sentence.

4 table

Category	Standard language	Transcriptions	English transliteration
Noun	bog‘lov	<i>bajlāv</i>	connection
Adjective	ochofat	<i>ačapat</i>	rapacious
Number	yetti	<i>žeti</i>	seven
Verb	chirillamoq	<i>čārillamāq</i>	to squawk
Pronoun	bu	<i>būl</i>	this
Adverb	chippa	<i>čippa</i>	complete
conjunction	magar	<i>māgār</i>	if

English transliteration

Translation of phonetic dialects into English has many other advantages (unlike lexical, semantic dialects):

- 1) the manifestation of dialects mainly in the form of a lemma;
- 2) differentiation of dialects from the literary language through phonemes;
- 3) commonality of dialectal semes;

4) There is a high probability of creating a single translation database for the online database into English (and other languages, for example, Russian).

The results of our study show that, as in any other language, the relatively large number of nouns in Uzbek grammar has led to the lexematic translation of most phonetic dialects into English.

Combined translation of dialects with lexical distinguishing features into English. The dialects that make up the Uzbek national language have several polysemantic meanings, reflecting the subtleties of meaning that we do not observe in the structure of the standard language: "bir majdān" (a short time), "būjūr" (lateral), "čappāti" (thin bread made from thin raised dough), "bežārim" (Active and naughty, person who fidgets or always gets in the way, mainly a child). When translating such speech units into English, implementing direct lexical translation may lead to incomplete disclosure or distortion of understanding of all terms of the dialect. In our opinion, it is advisable to translate such lexical dialects mainly in a complex form. Then, any other native speaker who studies the Turkic languages and their dialects would avoid mistakes in their studies, understanding the whole meaning of the dialect in context. So, with this translation method, central attention is paid to the compound translations of lexical dialects from the standard language into English. We have seen that such dialects are in the minority in numbers. Noun group – 70, adjective word group – 2 number word group – 1, pronoun word group - no, verb word group - 3, adverb word group - 1 and was not Conjunction, Modal words, Exclamative sentence. }

5 table

Category	Standard language	Transcription	Combined translation
noun	bedov	<i>bedāv</i>	Playful horse
adjective	chatanoq	<i>čatanak</i>	Someone who walks on his feet
number	-	-	-
verb	yigirmoq	<i>ijirmāq</i>	Preparation by weaving from wool
Pronoun	pukka	<i>pūkkā</i>	Deep surface state of the bone, semantics here are so-so

Combined translation of dialects

Uzbek dialects are one of the rich sources of the Uzbek standard language, like all standard languages of the Turkic language group, and local dialects, in turn, differ from other regions in particular national culture, customs, and beliefs [16]. For the meaning that lexemes carry in the translation process, the primary attention is paid to the information carrier of the word about the national culture, and the goal of interpretive translation is achieved. Our research shows that most of the lexemes translated by this method of English translation belong to word groups.: ābdasta – a long and slender faucet used for face and hand washing with a wide belly and a narrow neck; “ābroyan” – Palov when cooking rice add rice to the pot (water is added to fried meat onions and carrots and carrots are pressed again before adding rice; “žavran ātālā” – The flour is fried in oil and cooked in water; “ūkkavār” – Here swearing is sometimes used in the Boysun dialect as caressing; “Šrēm (žer)” – Dry, crumbly sticky soil; “pūkkā” – The deep surface-facing state of the lover means Etc. in connection with the life of the Uzbek people, their national views, everyday vocabulary and ethnographic traditions. Although such dialects make up the majority of Uzbek dialects, it has been recorded in our research area that a limited part of the Surkhandarya (Baysun) dialect is a minority in categories: Nouns – 74, Adjectives – 7 ta, Number – no, Pronoun – 1, Verb – 13, Adverb – 1 and Conjunction, Modal words – 1, Exclamative sentence – 2, Interjection – 1, and so on, it is seen that the interpretation provides the translation.

Category	Standard language	Transcription	Semantic translation (annotated translation)
Noun	-	<i>čääčvösär</i>	muscular meat beef, according to the people eat muscle beef spot her owner grows hair
Adjective	-	<i>šiqšiqqa</i>	presence of backlashes in bone joints
Verb	-	<i>egin bermāq</i>	Push with different parts of the body such as the sleeve part

Semantic translation of dialects

Conclusion. Considering that the translation of Uzbek dialects into another (English) language was not developed in monographic terms [17], the following conclusion was made:

Two stages should be organized in developing machine translation of Uzbek dialects and, in the first stage, creating a lexeme dictionary in the context of dialects related to each region.

In the context highlighted during the first stage, the development of three types of dialects present in the dictionary: the standard language, phonemic, and phonetic graphics, ensures that the base of the dialect online dictionary will serve any audience: an audience that explores the Turkic languages in synchronous and diachronic aspects;

The fact that when analyzing lexical, conjugated, and annotated translations of Uzbek dialects in the context of categories, nouns, and verbs reflecting personality, subject, and state of action occupy the most prominent place indicates the need to provide more straightforward solutions related to the translation of these categories between Uzbek dialects[18];

And lexical, compound, and annotated translations of Uzbek dialects enable representatives of other languages studying Uzbek not only to delve into various spiritual subtleties of the language but also to get to know the culture, mentality, traditions, and ethnography of this particular people.

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СЎЗ САНЪАТИ ХАЛҚАРО ЖУРНАЛИ

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Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
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